

Transition metal dichalcogenide metamaterials with atomic precision

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Abbreviated abstract: Here I will discuss our novel anisotropic wet etching method that allows scalable fabrication of TMD metamaterials with atomic precision, combined with traditional nanolithography techniques. [1] We show that TMDs can be etched along certain crystallographic axes, such that the obtained edges are atomically sharp and exclusively zigzag-terminated. This allow us to fabricate interesting hexagonal nanostructures of predefined order and complexity, including few nanometer thin nanoribbons and nanojunctions.

Related publications:

– B. Munkhbat et al, Nature Comm., 11, 4604 (2020)

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TMDC: Transition Metal Dichalcogenides (vdW materials)

MX_2 :

MoS₂ mineral rock

Key properties:

- Excellent platform for light-matter interactions
- 15-20% absorption at room T!
- Monolayer, thickness <1nm
- Interesting exciton physics
- Relatively stable
- Relatively simple to fabricate
- **Existance of trions!**

M (Metal): Mo, W, Ta ...
X (Chalcogen): S, Se, Te ...

Unique physical and chemical properties, including:

- Semiconducting (excitonic) property
- Optical (high absorption)
- Availability of reactive sites for redox reactions etc.,
- Multifunctional 1D zigzag edges

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One-Dimensional Metallic Edge States in MoS₂

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REPORTS

Identification of Active Edge Sites for Electrochemical H₂ Evolution from MoS₂ Nanocatalysts

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MoS₂ Nanoribbons: High Stability and Unusual Electronic and Magnetic Properties

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Abstract: First-principles computations were carried out to predict the stability and magnetic and electronic properties of MoS₂ nanoribbons with either zigzag or armchair-terminated edges. Zigzag nanoribbons show the ferromagnetic and metallic behavior, irrespective of the ribbon width and thickness. Armchair nanoribbons are nonmagnetic and semiconducting, and the band gaps converge to a constant value of ~0.56 eV as the ribbon width increases. The higher stability of MoS₂ nanoribbons, compared with the experimentally available triangular MoS₂ nanocrystals, invites the experimental realization of such novel ribbons in true nanoscale.

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How do we create exclusively "multi-functional zigzag edges" in TMDCs?

Exfoliation and Transfer

Nanolithography:
EBL, FIB etc.,

Wet-etching

Circular: mixture of armchair and zigzag

Hexagonal: Only zigzag edges

TEM and EELS study: Only zigzag edges

B. Munkhbat et al, Nature Comm., 11, 4604 (2020)

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Nanostructured 2D material: TMD WS₂

Advanced nanostructures: Ultrathin sub-5 nm nanoribbons and nanojunctions are extremely challenging to fabricate. These structures are comparable in size to small Bohr radius TMD excitons and hence will introduce quantum confinement effects.

Only the "right" edges: zigzag edges are the ones which are catalytically active, ferromagnetic, and conductive.

Nonlinear optics at the edge: the symmetry break at the edge naturally leads to emergence of second order nonlinear coefficient and thus will boost optical non-linearities, e.g. second harmonic generation (SHG). Combined with atomic sharpness, tight confinement, and resonant nano-photonics effects, TMD metamaterials promise to say a new word in nano-optics.

Sounds interesting?

What's next?, a lot!!!

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